

Retail Façade Change Detection via Street-level Imagery

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Summary

Retail stores are a primary setting for urban consumption, playing a crucial role in shaping urban economic vitality. However, current research on the quantitative study of retail façade environments and their spatio-temporal evolution remains limited. This study proposes a retail façade representation framework based on street level imagery, combining viewpoint alignment with three complementary models—DINOv3, SegFormer, and CIELAB—to capture the multidimensional semantic and visual features of retail façades. Using Liverpool, one of the

UK’s leading and economically vibrant cities, as an example, the framework identifies spatio-temporal patterns of retail transformation and renewal hotspots, and systematically compares the performance of the three modelling approaches. The findings provide valuable insights into urban retail dynamics and offer methodological support for urban and business analysis.

KEYWORDS: Urban transformation, Retail façade, Street-level imagery, Spatio-temporal analysis

1 Introduction

Retail stores are widely considered as a representative indicator of national and regional consumption levels (Fildes et al., 2022). Recent research further demonstrates that they play a crucial role in shaping street life, supporting pedestrian-centric urban functions, and fostering social interaction (Talen and Park, 2022). These findings highlight the close link between retail activity, urban economic vitality, and broader urban development patterns (Wrigley and Dolega, 2011). Consequently, scholars in geography and urban planning are increasingly focusing on micro-scale analysis of retail dynamics (Hillier, 2007; Sevtsuk, 2020).

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Previous research has primarily focused on accessibility and spatial interaction to examine how the urban physical environment influences retail activity (Lynch, 1964; Sevtsuk, 2014). For instance, some studies have relied on credit card transaction data or point-of-interest (POI) data and applied a range of machine learning methods to explore the relationship between shopping behaviour and retail distribution (Yoshimura et al., 2022), quantify retail cluster patterns (Orr et al., 2023), and develop new classifications of retail space (Dolega et al., 2021). These results have further facilitated the assessment of retail changes on a larger spatial scale (Ballantyne et al., 2023). However, such studies heavily rely on economic indicators and cross-sectional data, which constrains their ability to capture changes in the street level retail environment. This represents a key limitation given that changes in the retail landscape are inherently dynamic and have a significant impact on local consumer behaviour over time (Amin and Badruddoza, 2025).

In recent years, large-scale street-level imagery has become an important source of urban research, encompassing both user-generated and platform-mediated visual data (Hou et al., 2024). These data allow for observation of streetscapes and building features from a human-centred perspective, and help in measuring spatio-temporal change (Biljecki and Ito, 2021). Researchers have leveraged street-level imagery to detect building heights (Liu et al., 2025), classify façade materials (Chen et al., 2025), and estimate urban morphology (Pang and Biljecki, 2022). Moreover, longitudinal street-level imagery has been used to assess fine-grained changes in roads and buildings over time (Liu et al., 2025), as well as broader processes of urbanisation and landscape improvement (Liang et al., 2023). Nevertheless, despite the widespread adoption of street-level imagery in urban environmental studies, research specifically focusing on changes in the physical characteristics of retail façades and their spatio-temporal evolution remains limited. In particular, the close relationship between retail façade transformation and urban economic dynamics has yet to be systematically explored.

To address this research gap, this study proposes a retail façade representation learning framework that enables the robust extraction of both semantic indicators and visual perceptual features through view alignment. This approach can quantify the dynamic changes in the characteristics of fixed-location retail façades over time. Using large-scale street-level imagery of Liverpool as an example, and incorporating POI data as a benchmark, we examine the spatio-temporal evolution of retail façades over a ten-year period from 2015 to 2025.

2 Data and methodology

2.1 Study data

The data used in this study are obtained from Geographic Data Service (GeoDS), which is part of Smart Data Research UK (SDR UK). The dataset consists of two complementary components. The first is a nationwide, multi-year POI dataset covering the United Kingdom. Each POI contains detailed information, including its geographic location, business name, function category, and operating duration.

The second component comprises corresponding street-level imagery. These images directly show how retail stores have changed over time, capturing subtle changes in the appearance of retail

façades, such as store name, retail function, and visual colour. POI records and street-level images are linked through shared Premised IDs, each representing a unique retail location with fixed geographic coordinates.

Figure 1 presents representative examples of the street-level imagery used in this study, with each row illustrating the multi-year evolution of retail façades at the same address.

Local Bank → Toy Shop

Façade Updates

Take Away Meals → Fast Food

Restaurant Remains Unchanged

Figure 1: Street Level Imagery Data Example

2.2 Indicator extraction and change detection

We first extract two representative indicators from POI data: (1) the number of functional changes at each place between 2015 and 2025, and (2) the number of vacant years between 2015 and 2025. These indicators serve as a complementary, non-visual benchmark for assessing retail dy-

namics.

To ensure comparability of retail façades across different times and perspectives, we employ RANSAC-Flow, an efficient geometric image alignment method (Shen et al., 2020). Before applying the model to the full dataset, we fine-tune it using 2000 pairs of retail façade images. This model significantly helps reduce geometric distortions caused by variations in camera perspective, distance, and shooting conditions, and effectively reduce noise in subsequent analyses.

Following view alignment, we quantify retail façade changes using three complementary approaches and compare their respective performance:

(1) DINOv3.

DINOv3 is a family of general-purpose visual foundation models that produce high-quality, dense feature representations (Siméoni et al., 2025). In this study, DINOv3 captures high-level semantic and structural changes in retail façades, showing sensitivity to visually and functionally meaningful transformations such as signage, overall façade configuration, and functional change.

(2) SegFormer.

SegFormer is a Transformer-based semantic segmentation model introduced by NVIDIA in 2021 (Xie et al., 2021) and has demonstrated strong performance in street-level imagery segmentation tasks (Zhao et al., 2024; Choi and Kang, 2025). We apply SegFormer for pixel-level semantic segmentation to extract façade elements (e.g., buildings, signage, and windows) and quantify changes in semantic composition over time.

(3) CIELAB colour space.

CIELAB is a perceptually uniform colour space designed to approximate human visual perception (Zhang et al., 1996). Owing to its robustness to illumination variation, we use CIELAB to extract low-level visual features of retail façades and measure changes in dominant colour schemes over time, complementing the semantic and structural indicators derived from the other models.

Figure 2 illustrates the overall workflow and representative visual examples of the image processing results. All extracted indicators are subsequently aggregated to H3 resolution 11 hexagonal units by computing mean values and are visualised to support spatial analysis.

Figure 2: Image Processing Workflow

3 Results

Figure 3 visualises the spatial distribution of two representative POI-based indicators between 2015 and 2025: the average number of retail functional changes and the average duration of vacancy. Figure 3a shows that across most central areas, retail façades experienced an average of approximately 1.0–1.9 functional changes over the ten-year period, with the spatial extent of change gradually expanding outward from the urban core towards major commercial streets. The most pronounced concentration of functional change is observed in the core area surrounding Liverpool One (highlighted by the boxed area), a major waterfront district characterised by shopping, dining, and entertainment uses, and one of the most intensively renewed retail areas in Liverpool over the past decade, where retail functions underwent two or more changes on average.

Figure 3b presents the spatial distribution of retail vacancy duration, measured in years. The results indicate that vacancy duration in most areas generally remained below one year across the majority of the city. The highest levels of vacancy are concentrated around the intersection of Church Street and Hanover Street, in the vicinity of Liverpool Central Station, where average vacancy duration reaches 3.25 years or more. This pattern extends into nearby areas, with vacancy durations frequently exceeding one year.

(a) Number of Retail Function Changes from 2015 to 2025

(b) Length of Retail Stores Vacancies (in Years) from 2015 to 2025

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of representative indicators derived from POI data in Liverpool

Figure 4 presents the spatial visualisation of image-based indicators extracted using the three modelling approaches. Guided by POI-derived ground truth, the results are divided into two subsets. Figures 4a, 4c, and 4e corresponds to *function change* = 0, where all image pairs represent the same POI function over time, indicating no change in retail ownership or tenancy. Figures 4b, 4d, and 4f corresponds to *function change* = 1, which includes only image pair comparisons in which a retail unit has been replaced by a new store.

Under the *function change* = 0 condition, the results reveal substantial renewal activity in Liverpool’s city centre even in the absence of functional replacement. Both the SegFormer- and CIELAB-based indicators exhibit strong spatial clustering around Lime Street Station and the Royal Albert Dock, reflecting pronounced changes in façade structure and colour composition. In contrast, DINOv3, which captures higher-dimensional semantic differences, does not exhibit a similar concentration pattern in these areas.

Compared with the preceding condition, the *function change* = 1 results show a similar spatial clustering only in the SegFormer-based indicator. For DINOv3 and CIELAB, the overall intensity of change is significantly weaker than under the *function change* = 0 condition, and the high values are mainly concentrated in the core urban area, with a more limited spatial range.

(a) Result of DINOv3 (Function Change=0)

(b) Result of DINOv3 (Function Change=1)

(c) Result of SegFormer (Function Change=0)

(d) Result of SegFormer (Function Change=1)

(e) Result of CIE Lab (Function Change=0)

(f) Result of CIE Lab (Function Change=1)

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of image analysis results from different models in Liverpool

4 Conclusion

This study proposes a street-level imagery-based retail façade representation learning framework to capture subtle spatiotemporal changes in the retail environment in Liverpool, UK, between 2015 and 2025. First, we align images to a consistent perspective and then apply three complementary models, namely DINOv3, SegFormer, and CIELAB, to extract diverse façade representations reflecting semantic, structural, and perceptual dimensions of retail change. Secondly, by integrating with POI-derived ground truth, the results show that significant visual changes occur even without retail functional replacement. Thirdly, our findings further reveal significant spatial heterogeneity in Liverpool’s retail façade renovations. Despite relatively low retail replacement, the intensity and magnitude of visual changes are concentrated in the city center, major commercial corridors, and key transport hubs. More broadly, this study highlights the crucial value of image-based indicators in uncovering retail development dynamics that cannot be observed solely from economic or cross-sectional data. By integrating multiple variables into a composite index in the future, we are able to capture multidimensional differences in retail environments under dynamic change. This approach enables a more comprehensive understanding of how various aspects of retail façades evolve over time. Furthermore, by extending the proposed framework to a larger spatial scale—such as nationwide analysis across the UK—and linking retail façade changes to geodemographic characteristics, future research can offer new insights into the processes shaping urban retail transformation and development.

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6 Biography

Haixiao Liu is a first-year PhD student in the Department of Geography and Planning at University of Liverpool, and is also affiliated with the Geographic Data Service. His research interests focus on geotagged image data and geodemographics, with an emphasis on using large-scale image data to investigate spatio-temporal change across urban and national contexts.

Rahul Savani is a Professor in the Department of Computer Science at the University of Liverpool. He works on problems at the interface of economics/finance and computer science. He has worked extensively on equilibrium computation for game-theoretic models of strategic interaction. He has also worked as a consultant on a variety of algorithmic trading projects. He is a member of the Economics and Computation Research Group.

Zi Ye is Lecturer in Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool. She is based in the Geographic Data Science Lab and the Geographic Data Service (GeoDS). Her research explores how people engage with changing neighbourhoods, particularly in relation to household finance, retail geographies, and broader transformations of the urban landscape.

Zihan Yin is a Senior Data Scientist at the Geographic Data Service, University of Liverpool. Her

research interests lie at the intersection of applied microeconomics and spatial data science, with a particular focus on econometric analysis of geographic patterns, spatial visualization techniques, and the application of quantitative methods to understand socioeconomic disparities and behaviors across different regions.

Alex Singleton is Professor of Geographic Information Science at the University of Liverpool and Director of the Geographic Data Service. His research sits at the boundary between the social and computational sciences; and has extended a tradition of area classification within Urban Analytics where he has developed an empirically informed critique of the ways in which geodemographic methods (unsupervised machine learning) can be refined for effective yet ethical use; and how systems comprising artificial intelligence can assist in public resource allocation applications. This research has developed from substantive interests around the social, spatial and temporal dimensions of urban systems; specifically focused on inequalities of opportunities.

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